

IDENTIFICATION OF EDUCATIONAL PURPOSES IN UNIVERSITY CLASSES

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Abstract. *The main element of the methodological system, which determines the solution of all questions of methodology, is learning objectives. The work of B.S. Bloom [2] is devoted to this issue. Based on this work, this article touches upon the issue of identifying learning objectives in university classes. Discussions were held with students; assignments were made to identify objectives during classes.*

Keywords: *aim, discussion, knowledge, comprehension, personal aim, purpose, result, object aim, value.*

This article highlights the following range of issues relevant to analyzing the possibilities of using active methods in teaching special subjects:

- construction of the system of active methods in accordance with the specificity of the subject content;
- specifying the requirements of active learning methods through a variety of didactic strategies based on the teacher's choice of systems of learning tasks in the course of the subject;
- specification of the requirements of active learning methods in situations of joint learning activities organized using the system of forms of educational institutions of the teacher with students and students' interaction with each other.

A goal is an anticipated result of activity, an object projection of the future, a subjective image of the desired, outrunning the reflection of events in human consciousness.

Scientists develop taxonomies of learning objectives - systematized banks of sub-objectives (tasks) corresponding to certain educational areas or a specific training course [2;7]. Formulated in terms of learning objectives and arranged in order of achievement, the sub-objectives help the teacher to achieve the overall goals of the course.

According to the main didactic principle governing the educational process, each student's learning should take place on the basis of and with regard to his or her personal learning goals. Today, various educational actors are involved in setting goals. In the classification of goals, we can distinguish state, normative, social, national-religious, and educational goals.

Depending on educational paradigms and didactic systems, educational goals may include the goals of knowledge acquisition, skills and abilities development.

There is a science of goal setting - mathematics, which proves the necessity of the initial stage of any activity with the discussion of final goals, i.e. the expected fruits of the activity.

Here is an example of a taxonomy of learning objectives, the author of which is a recognized expert in this field, American pedagogue and psychologist B.S. Bloom.

1.Knowledge: knowledge of specifics; knowledge of terminology; knowledge of specific facts; knowledge of ways and meanings of using specifics; knowledge of conventions; knowledge of directions and sequences of development; knowledge of classifications and categories;

knowledge of criteria; knowledge of methodology; knowledge of universals and abstractions in the specialty; knowledge of principles and generalizations; knowledge of theories and structures.

2. Understanding: translation; interpretation; extrapolation.

3. Synthesis: creating a coherent message; creating a plan or proposition of a set of operations; deduction of a set of abstract relations.

4. Evaluation: inferring under conditions of internal evidence; inferring under conditions of external criteria.

Goal setting in learning is the establishment by students and teachers of the goals and objectives of learning at certain stages of learning. It is necessary for the design of student's educational actions and are connected with the external social order, educational standards, with the specifics of internal conditions of learning - the level of students' development, their learning motivations, pedagogical views of the teacher, etc. The goal setting in learning is a part of the completely educational process.

In personality-oriented learning, goal setting goes through the entire educational process, performing in it the functions of motivation of student's activity, structural stabilization of the educational process, and diagnostics of learning results.

Goal setting determines the structural basis of activity programs not only for the student, but also for the teacher and the completely educational institution, allowing to determine an adequate teaching technology and a system of criteria for evaluating the results obtained. The goal of activity is an anticipated result. The goal can be general and specific, distant and near, external and internal, realized or not. To set a goal means to predict, to forecast the anticipated result. A well-understood and labelled goal "leads" the person who formulated it to the appropriate result. Often the goals declared in educational programs differ significantly from the real-life orientations of students, which is the reason for the discrepancy between the desired and actual in learning. To prevent this undesirable phenomenon it is necessary to introduce students into the procedure of educational goal setting from the beginning of the study of a course, section or topic.

In solving this technological task, there are the following stages:

1. diagnosis of students' goals (conducted by means of oral interview, written questionnaire, testing, observations, expert surveys, etc.).

2. analysis and systematization of the obtained data

3. construction of individual technological lines of student learning in the general technological line of the teacher.

The absence of an initial set of goals (a list of ready-made goals) makes it possible to identify a person's actual personally significant goals. When we offer a ready-made list of goals students can create their own hierarchy from the proposed options. This approach allows us to obtain generalized data on the dominant directions of goal setting in the group.

Discussion. Do the goals indicated by the student always really coincide with his/her intentions?

After analyzing the data received from students, the instructor gets a complete picture of preferences, taking into account which he/she formulates priority learning goals.

The following groups of student goals are possible: personal goals - comprehension of educational goals; gaining faith in oneself, in one's potentialities; realization of specific individual abilities; subject objectives - formation of a positive attitude to the studied subject; knowledge of

the basic concepts, phenomena and laws included in the studied subject; development of skills to use simple devices; solving typical or creative problems on the subject;

creative goals - compiling a collection of problems; composing a natural science treatise; constructing a technical model; drawing a picture; cognitive goals - cognition of objects of the surrounding reality; studying ways of solving arising problems; mastering the skills of working with primary sources; setting up an experiment; conducting experiments; organisational goals - mastering the skills of self-organisation of learning activities; the ability to set a goal; planning activities; developing group work skills; mastering discussion techniques.

Different types of goals can be present in one formulation, as the achievement of the same goal often requires the use of several personal qualities of the student. Here are the formulations of educational goals that contain creative, cognitive, organizing and action components at the same time: "Describe the facts obtained through observation about sugar crystals" (physics); "Identify and depict the logical structure of the concept "human being" (philosophy); "Build a classification of cultural traditions of the Karakalpak people" (history).

In order for the final list of the main educational goals formulated by the teacher on the basis of student goals to be provided with the conditions of achievement, their preliminary analysis is necessary in the following directions:

- the ability to evoke in the student exactly those expectations and activities in which they are interested.

- identification of goals that will solve the actual educational tasks in relation to specific students in the current conditions;

- adjusting the level of difficulty to the individual characteristics of students and their developmental level (biology - "Determine how a pine tree differs from a spruce tree" or "Find out why a spruce tree differs from a pine tree").

After determining the set objectives, a basic technological map is designed on their basis, including the system of lessons on the topic, forms, methods, selected material, and necessary teaching aids. With the help of this map, an educational programme for the course is designed, a thematic plan, a working programme of the course, and methodological developments are drawn up.

The organization of goal setting includes three interrelated activities: the student's activity to develop an individual technological map (a group of personal learning goals); the teacher's activity to design a basic technological map; their joint activity to create a technological map.

In educational goal, setting there is a range of levels of formulated goals - from element goals to semantic and prospective goals. The achievement of a goal depends on the way in which it has been set. The formulation of goals should be in a form that allows checking the level of their achievement. Thus, formulations such as "to obtain systematized information about fractions" or "to form children's historical thinking" are not goals, as they set only the direction of activity, but not its result - the product of educational activity. On the contrary, goals such as "develop their own versions of the origin of fractions" or "ask students to list historical events in their lives and argue their historicity" set the final product of students' activity, which can be diagnosed and evaluated.

Formulating a goal in the form of a final educational product is the most effective way of goal setting. Initial goals have their own specificity. The following features characterize them:

1. emotional entry into the educational process (conversations, stories, etc.).

2. diagnosis of students' characteristics: favourite activities, degree of creative orientation, level of preparedness, self-organisation, etc.

3. creation (construction) of the image of the upcoming academic year.

At the beginning of teaching a particular academic discipline, the goals of the teacher are as follows:

- to help students to create a holistic image of the academic subject (to find out its meaning, why it is needed, what it consists of, what its features are; to formulate the most interesting questions): students can be offered to make a scheme, draw a symbol or a concept of the subject:

- In order to form an image of activity in a new course or its topic, students should be asked to perform basic activities, e.g. invent a story, draw a geometric figure, etc.

- through the initial educational products created by the students and the activities they have tried out, lead them to set individual goals for the course for a foreseeable period of time: - to draw up a syllabus for the semester, incorporating the course objectives proposed by the students.

A special place is occupied by the methodology of teaching students goal-setting.

The conditions of the goal-setting procedure:

- presence of cognitive aspiration of the student;
- determination of the subject of his/her goal;
- the student's ability to determine his/her relationship with the subject of the goal;
- representation of the image of the expected result of their activity in relation to the object of the goal;

- verbal formulation of the goal;

- anticipation of how the goal will be achieved;

- availability of means to achieve the goal;

- correlation of the obtained results with the goal;

- adjustment of the goal.

For a student to set a personal educational goal in the educational field the following procedures are necessary:

1. building a personal relationship of the student with the object of goal-setting (thing, concept, process, phenomenon), which reveals and actualizes his/her personal qualities related to the object (e.g., love of nature in the study of plants).

2. marking in the object what it is connected with the personality of the subject who cognizes it;

3. choosing a type of relationship or activity to interact with the object, for example, studying its chemical, mathematical, ethical properties.

On the usual subject material, students are offered the tasks:

"Formulate your goals for studying civil law", "Make a plan for observing a burning candle", "Recall your main difficulties in composing a computer programme and the ways in which you overcame them"

Such assignments, on the one hand, solve subject tasks, on the other hand, ensure that students master the skills of self-organisation of education.

Discussion. Will the instructor be able to teach students differently if they all set their individual goals?

- Scientific substantiation of active methods of teaching special subjects is one of the most developed and at the same time the most significant tasks of modern teaching methodology.

The practice of building an independent state gives birth to a new concept of personal development. This circumstance has put forward before all sciences and before the higher school of the country the requirement to prepare and realize the transition to qualitatively new conditions of education and training of specialists.

This social requirement is dictated not only by society's daily needs for constant improvement of the quality of specialists, but also by a more social task - to bring the state of education in line with the new goals of transforming the capabilities of each person. The main condition for the intensification of social and economic progress is the formation of each member of society as a comprehensively developed, civically responsible individual. This way of accelerating social progress through the active formation of its carriers requires a radical restructuring of the goals, content, methods and technology of the entire education system. In terms of its scale of influence on the personality, the learning process must become effective.

Achievement of such a goal implies, in particular, considerable efforts in the direction of scientific development of active learning methods based on modern scientific data of each science. The basic provisions developed in this field of sciences, about the active role of consciousness in the practice of people at all stages of its formation, about carrying out the new formation of psyche only on the basis of a person's own activity in the conditions of interaction with other people - this will create a scientific foundation for active teaching methods.

However, it is impossible not to notice the large gap that exists today between the degree of validity and use of active methods in teaching the sciences themselves and those of its provisions, which are fully realized only in scientific research, but not in teaching.

Students still learn knowledge in learning situations, the principles of organisation of which are very far from the principles proclaimed by science itself and constituting the scientific foundation of active learning methods. This gap between the content of knowledge and the approach to the organisation of its assimilation cannot be eliminated by a simple volitional effort. To overcome it, it is necessary:

1. Special work on scientific substantiation of the use of active methods in teaching special subjects, expansion of the practice of their use and its analysis.

2. Further development of each science, in particular, changing its approaches to the interpretation of learning activity. The specificity of teaching is usually seen in the fact that it is a preparatory activity. In this direction, it is distinguished from play and labour. The process of teaching is opposed to creativity as a process of creating a new, socially valuable product. However, as long as teaching only prepares a person for labour, for further creative professional work, it cannot act as a transformative activity.

Summary: The article is devoted to the study of the issues of identification of educational goals in teaching special subjects in higher education. Here the possibilities of using active methods in teaching subjects according to their goals are analyzed: personal, creative, cognitive and others.

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